

DR. THEODORE CORWIN thought the intra-tracheal injections most valuable. Patients could be taught to make the injections themselves, using a long dropper and injecting fifteen or twenty minims two or three times within ten minutes and repeating this every half hour or hour, so long as the cough was annoying. He used vaselin or other oil in combination with menthol, 1 or 2 per cent, camphor 1 per cent, or anything that might be desired. For office treatment the tracheal syringe was preferable, giving doses of one or two drams. It should be preceded by a downward spray of 2 per cent menthol to render the larynx less sensitive to manipulation with the syringe.

DR. RICHARDS added that some years ago he used oils of one kind or another, and instructed his patients to use nebulizers. He has reached the conclusion that oils are nearly valueless. It was better to employ something corresponding as nearly as possible in specific gravity to that of the normal serum.

DR. THOMPSON, in closing the discussion, said that when Dr. Harris sent out his circular letter asking for suggestions concerning this meeting he thought it wise to have several papers concerning the treatment of the diseases of the upper air passages. Dr. Beck agreed to discuss the scientific side, while he took the therapeutic side of the question. He had endeavored to discuss the matter from the point of view of every-day practice. The most important point, and one which he would reiterate, was expressed in the opening sentence of his paper: "One-half of all the diseases it is our daily work to treat are curable by medicinal means alone."

DR. BECK, in closing the discussion, said about 5 per cent of his cases were amenable to non-surgical treatment. He had reference to diseases of the upper respiratory tract not those of the trachea.

Tuberculosis of the Middle Ear. DR. H. H. BRIGGS, Asheville, N. C.

The frequency of tuberculosis of the middle ear in persons suffering from tuberculosis elsewhere in the body has been placed at twenty-five per cent. Of 1,500 school children examined by Westmacotte, 2 per cent were found to have tuberculosis of the middle ear. The disease is probably of far greater frequency than statistics show, and the true diagnosis is often mistaken because its onset is so insidious that attention is not easily called to the condition and no observation is made. Moreover, when the case presents itself the condition usually has passed from that of a pure tuberculous process and becomes a mixed infection, the symptoms of the suppurative condition making the true nature of the initial disease. The careless manner of classifying all discharging ears as suppurative otitis media, without recourse to the microscopic or inoculation tests, is unfortunate.

The middle ear must be regarded as belonging anatomically and bacteriologically to the upper respiratory tract, as insisted upon by Goldstein, who considers primary tuberculous infection of the middle ear of respiratory origin.

Among the predisposing factors may be classed general debilitating diseases, the hereditary influence of tuberculosis, syphilis, association with tuberculous individuals, unhygienic environment, over-crowding, poor

food, cachexia,—in short, any condition of surroundings or constitution which induces a lowering of the systemic power to combat infection. Among the predisposing causes of more immediate influence may be regarded (1) the existence of a tuberculous lesion elsewhere in the body, especially pulmonary tuberculosis with cavitation, and tuberculous disease of the glandular system; (2) abnormal conditions of the upper respiratory tract, including the presence of naso-pharyngeal adenoid growths which have been shown by microscopic examination and inoculation tests to be the frequent seat of a latent tuberculosis; (3) infancy and childhood offer a predisposition for various reasons.

The channels of infection are: 1. Mechanical, through the Eustachian tube, either air-borne or introduced into the tympanic cavity by the aid of particles of mucus or foreign matter during the acts of swallowing, coughing, sneezing, or blowing the nose. 2. Infection along the Eustachian tube by other than mechanical means. 3. Through the blood channels. 4. Through the lymphatics. 5. Via the external auditory canal. 6. By extension of an intra-cranial infection through the internal auditory canal, Fallopiian canal or the labyrinth. This is mentioned as merely a possibility.

To the author the mechanical theory of infection, especially secondary, seems simplest, easiest and most probable in the great majority of cases. The greatest number of cases occur in early childhood and advanced phthisis, when the conditions favorable to the mechanical passage of infectious material through the Eustachian tube are at their maximum.

Clinically, two rather distinct forms of tuberculosis of the middle ear manifest themselves,—acute and chronic. In each may be found all the changes, from slight infiltration of the mucous membrane to extensive necrosis of the temporal bone. Rapid loss of tissue is characteristic of the acute form, resulting from ulceration of the tubercles throughout the mucosa. In the chronic form the process runs an asthenic course, and infiltration, caseation and necrosis follow less rapidly and with more characteristic tuberculous sequence.

The essential symptom which differentiates tuberculous otitis from other forms is the absence of pain. Even though the destructive process is rapid and the appearance of the *membrana per se* simulates an acute purulent otitis there is seldom any complaint of pain.

In determining the diagnosis, the family history should be carefully considered with regard to tuberculosis, and the patient's habits, residence, environment should be ascertained to determine whether there has been an undue exposure to tuberculous persons or unhygienic surroundings. Facial paralysis, especially in children, occurs in one-third of the cases, against one to two per cent in non-tuberculous conditions, and is of special diagnostic significance. The sanious and foul condition of the discharge, especially when particles of bone are incorporated, excites suspicion. Marked impairment of hearing, absence of headache, occurrence of hemorrhage, are considered by some as diagnostic points. Tuberculin injections and blood pressure changes (hypotension) are also considered. The only positive means of diagnosis, however, are (1) finding microscopically in the discharge or granulations the tubercle bacillus, or (2)

giant and epithelioid cells and caseation in the tissue. (3) By experimental inoculation, reproducing tuberculosis. The prognosis is, as a rule, unfavorable.

The treatment naturally divides itself into hygienic, dietetic, medical, and surgical, as the case indicates. The use of tuberculin has proved so successful in so many forms of tuberculosis that no tuberculous process in any way localized can be considered invariably to contra-indicate its use. The author could see no reason why it should not be indicated and of decided value in properly selected cases of tuberculosis of the middle ear.

DR. FRANK R. SPENCER mentioned a method of making the diagnosis of tuberculosis of the middle ear, consisting of cleansing the canal first, introducing an aspirator which he has brought from Berlin, aspirating and injecting the pus into a guinea-pig. The pus, when aspirated, might not show tubercle bacilli, but the organisms could be positively demonstrated after the injection into the guinea-pig by the examination of the animal's organs several weeks later.

Corrective Rhinoplasty. DR. LEE COHEN, Baltimore.

Published in full in the June, 1914, issue of THE LARYNGOSCOPE, p. 565.

DISCUSSION.

DR. JOHN O. ROE: "Dr. Cohen's paper is a verification of the old saying that 'imitation is the sincerest flattery.' I am sorry, indeed, to see that Dr. Cohen is inclined to give me scant recognition as the originator of subcutaneous plastic surgery in the correction of nasal deformities, for it must be recognized and distinctly understood that this method of correcting nasal deformities subcutaneously originated entirely with me.

"In describing the method of making the initial incision from the interior of the nose, Dr. Cohen says: 'For these submucous operations, then, incision as first advocated by Roe should be made within the vestibule of the nose.' I wish to say that this method is not simply advocated by me but, as a matter of fact, was originated by me. It is my method which Dr. Cohen has copied from start to finish, without the courtesy of giving credit for it.

"Dr. Cohen on one occasion had the privilege of witnessing my work, which I am always glad to show my confreres and which, as he stated at that time, was the incentive that gave him his special interest in the correction of nasal deformities. The second case that Dr. Cohen mentions in his paper—the case of the congenitally, over-sized nose, causing the young man so much annoyance and mental distress—Dr. Cohen had the courtesy to refer to me and came with the patient to my office to see the operation, which I performed at that time in his presence on May 30, 1912. In connection with this operation, he saw the distinct method of elevating the skin or 'undermining' it, as he chooses to term it, the forms of dressing necessary in these cases, the use of my saddle splint, which I have used from the beginning of this work, and the method of holding it in place with the strap of adhesive plaster across the face, the use of the strips or pieces of adhesive plaster under the saddle, one placed above the other, in order to produce extra-pressure at points where necessary, the